

First Level Master in Electoral Policy and Administration

Electoral Participation of Persons with Disabilities in 2021 General Election: Voices from Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia

Author *Mekebib Tadesse Assefa*

Lead Supervisor *Dr Luca Poltronieri Rossetti*

Second Supervisor *Dr Melvis Ndiloseh*

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Dedication

The value of time in this world is still inconclusively defined. However, it is known that time is a valuable asset in achieving tangible results and success. My thesis highlights the need for significant efforts to ensure full electoral participation of persons with disabilities in the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. Despite the challenging circumstances, those individuals with disabilities who are actively participating in the electoral process are a true inspiration. I dedicate this thesis to them.

Acknowledgments

There is nothing in this world that can make me forget the impact you've had on my life, whether it was good or bad. As I work on my thesis about Electoral Participation of Persons with Disabilities in the 2021 General Election, I want to take a moment to acknowledge everyone who has crossed my path, as you have all taught me to become a better version of myself. The value of your presence in my life is immeasurable, and I will always be grateful for it. Thank you all once again for everything, as your contributions have not only impacted my past but also continue to shape my present and future.

List of Abbreviations / Acronyms

ACDEG	African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance
ACHPR	African Charter on Human and People's Rights
ADC	African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance
AU	African Union
CEDAW	Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women
CRPD	Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
EHRC	Ethiopian Human Right Commission
FDRE	Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia
HoPR	House of People Representative
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICERD	International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination
IRI	International Republican Institute
NDI	National Democratic Institute
NEBE	National Election board of Ethiopia
PWDs	Person with Disabilities
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Right
UN	United Nations

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Abstract

Electoral participation is a fundamental human right that applies to all citizens, regardless of their disability status. However, in the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE), people with disabilities face discrimination and are unable to exercise their right to vote equally with other citizens.

FDRE has ratified several international and regional legal frameworks, including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), and the African Charter on Democracy, Elections, and Governance (ACDEG). Unfortunately, these legal frameworks were not effectively implemented during the 2021 General Election, leading to discrimination against PWDs.

The study found several examples of discrimination, including inaccessible voting materials, lack of representation of PWDs women and men, failure to provide assistive technology, a toxic political environment, and insufficient financial and empowering resources. These findings highlight the need for effective implementation of legal frameworks and practical measures to ensure the electoral participation of PWDs and eliminate discrimination.

Policy and legal reforms are necessary in Ethiopia to ensure electoral participation of PWDs, which include physical accessibility of polling stations and voting materials, training of election officials, awareness-raising campaigns, legal protection of PWDs, collaboration among government agencies and disability rights groups, amendments to electoral laws, harmonization of disability rights laws, adoption of legal frameworks, and provision of accessible information and communication. By implementing these measures, PWDs will be able to exercise their right to vote and participate fully in the democratic process.

It is essential that the Ethiopian government takes urgent action to implement these reforms before the next general election to uphold the rights of PWDs and promote a fair and inclusive electoral process for all citizens.

Keywords: Electoral participation, Human rights, PWDs, Discrimination, Legal frameworks, Inclusive electoral process, Policy reforms, Accessibility

1. Chapter One: Introduction and Background

This chapter introduces the details and examination of this thesis, including the significance of the research, problem statement, research questions, aim, objectives, and scope of the study. The research methodology is discussed, including the research design process, delimitation and limitations, and ethical and confidentiality considerations. Additionally, an organizational structure of the thesis work is provided, outlining the specific chapters, sections, and key themes that will be addressed. Overall, this chapter serves as a comprehensive introduction to the key elements of the thesis, providing readers with an overview of what they can expect from the research.

1.1 About the thesis

The right to electoral participation for Persons with disabilities has gained increasing recognition in recent years, as supported by various international treaties and conventions, including the African Charter on Human and People's Rights (ACHPR), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance (ADC), and Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR).

Despite this, Persons with disabilities continue to face significant barriers to their full participation in electoral processes. This study focuses on the 2021 General Election in the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia and explores the extent to which the existing international legal instruments, to which the FDRE is a signatory, were effectively implemented to guarantee the electoral participation rights of people with disabilities. The study was conducted by a student pursuing a Masters of Electoral Policy and Administration.

1.2 Significance of the Thesis

As general rule of thumb institutions working in the area and scholars have observed that national disability statistics grossly underestimate the number of persons with disabilities in their country than made by international organizations. The inferred from the global disability statistics pattern by international organization that persons with disabilities in Ethiopia, representing 17.6 per cent of the total population. (General Statistics Agency of Ethiopia , 2020) on the other hand, this percent is increase steadily as the populations ages increased. The rate

of electoral participation among people with disabilities is mandatory small which also varies with the type of disability. (Belt, 2022). Although some interventions have been implemented to address various barriers, their impact on the capacity of Person with disabilities (PWDs) to promote their electoral participate in elections remains unknown. (Virendrakumar, et al., 2018) Thus, Assessing the accessibility of national elections is important so that regulatory bodies can be kept up to date about the implementation of international and national legislations. On this thesis we will providing information to the National Election board of Ethiopia (NEBE) & Ethiopian human right commission (EHRC) though. They will use this information in discussions with policy-makers about the adequacy and acceptability of measures that could be taken to live up to the international conventions with regard to electoral participation in the near future.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

People with disabilities have historically faced discrimination in various facets of society in a lot of nations throughout the world, and Federal democratic republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) are no exception. PWDs are not using their right to electoral participation equally with other citizens, despite the fact that the FDRE Constitution grants everyone the right to vote without discrimination.

In case of FDRE the public's mindset appears to be distant from the propensity of choosing these individuals as members of the legislative bodies of the government at various levels. On the voters side the absence of accessible voter education, the accessibility of polling places and materials, the absence of a secret ballot, communication hurdles, and electoral violence are additional issues that may limit the involvement of people with disabilities in the electoral process. Even though sign language may be used for television commercials and other important programs, most of deaf or hearing-impaired people might not have access to televisions, as is the situation for many people with disabilities. Therefore, the issue that people with disabilities are not able to participate in elections on an equal footing with others due to the inaccessible nature of the electoral participation and facilities continues to exist.

In general, the main issues that need to be addressed in this thesis by bench marking the international convention accepted by FDRE are the invisibility of people with disabilities in the electoral participation arena of the 2021 general election of the Federal democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE), either by way of voting, by competing for office bench, or by actively participating in the political parties of their choice in federal level.

1.4 Research Questions

The major questions that this thesis seeks to address is

“Do the existing international legal instruments, to which the FDRE is a signatory as implemented in the 2021 general election, allow for effective guarantees of the electoral participation rights of people with disabilities?”

1.5 Aim, Objectives & Scope of the thesis

This thesis examine the legal and regulatory frameworks for electoral participation of persons with disabilities; evaluates the level of electoral participation of persons with disabilities; analyses how political parties processes include persons with disabilities as candidates and in leadership roles and the barriers that individuals with person with disabilities encountered when voting and to what extent they were present during the national elections in 21 June 2021 and 30 September 2021 in the FDRE. We also need to get a sense of what improvements they would like to see in order to make electoral participation easier for people with disabilities in the upcoming national elections.

1.6 Research Methodology

1.6.1 Research Design Process

The method of qualitative research known as interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) is fairly new and expanding quickly. Although it originated and is best recognized in psychology, those working in related fields in the human, social, and health sciences are increasingly adopting it. IPA is a qualitative research methodology devoted to examining how people interpret their significant life events. In that it is concerned with examining experience in its own terms, IPA is phenomenological. (Smith, et al., 2022) Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) the technique provides a systematic framework and explicit application principles that enable for comprehensive examination of relevant issues while also providing for plenty of flexibility to explore individuals' various experiences and perceptions. The method can be used to research previously unexplored phenomena in more depth or to investigate whole new fields of investigation. Although IPA shares many conceptual roots with classic phenomenological techniques, it differs most significantly in its emphasis on ideography. The technique may be valuable for researchers interested in in-depth analyses of convergence and divergence within individual participants' meaning creation. (Miller, et al., 2018) Thus thesis proposal research will employ as much as possible qualitative approaches

empowered by interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) through interviewing PWDs and organizations that promote and facilitate electoral participation. Also reviewing of literature on elections and electoral participation using desk analysis is also in order. On the other hand, quantitative approaches of analyses to evaluate the level of electoral participation will be under consideration of using as research methodology.

1.6.2 Delimitation & Limitation of the Thesis

Delimitation: The scope of this thesis is limited to the examination of the 2021 General Election in the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia and the extent to which international legal instruments guaranteeing the electoral participation rights of persons with disabilities were effectively implemented. The study will not delve into the overall situation of persons with disabilities in Ethiopia or the history of disability rights in the country. Additionally, the study will only focus on persons with disabilities who faced barriers to their participation in the electoral process and will not examine other types of discrimination faced by persons with disabilities in other spheres of life.

Limitation: This thesis faces several limitations. Firstly, the study was hindered by the difficulty in obtaining well-documented statistical data quickly regarding the entire population of persons with disabilities in the FDRE. Secondly, the author encountered communication challenges with some interviewees who had learning or cognitive disabilities, which we solved the limitation by the help of assisting personal. Thirdly, the author faced difficulties in connecting with parliamentary members with disabilities during the data gathering phase. Lastly, the study was conducted by a student pursuing a Masters of Electoral Policy and Administration, and the findings may be limited by the author's lack of experience and expertise in the field.

1.6.3 Ethical & Confidentiality Consideration of the Thesis

Prospective study participants were informed by the researchers that participation was completely voluntary and that they had the option to leave the study at any point if they so desired. By treating the participants' comments with a high degree of anonymity and without asking them to provide or write their names or other personal information, the researchers were able to safeguard their confidentiality. Instead of using actual identities, pen names were employed for participants and research sites to ensure that neither group could be identified by any identifiers.

1.7 Organizational structure of the thesis work

The thesis is structured into four main chapters. Chapter One introduces the primary concern of the thesis, setting the context and outlining the key issues that will be addressed. In Chapter Two, the literature review is presented, which forms the foundation for the research by examining and synthesizing existing documents on our topic. Chapter Three is about The International, Regional, and National Legal Frameworks Regarding the Electoral Rights of Persons with Disabilities. Chapter Four presents the critical survey and data, detailing the methodology and data collection techniques used in the study. This chapter also discusses the results of the research and provides an analysis of the findings. Finally, Chapter Five concludes the thesis by summarizing the key findings and presenting recommendations based on the research. This chapter provides a final overview of the study and highlights its implications and potential for further research in the field.

1.8 Conclusion of the Chapter

In conclusion, this chapter has provided an overview of the key details and elements of the thesis, which focuses on examining the electoral participation of persons with disabilities in the 2021 General Election in Ethiopia. Using interpretative phenomenological analysis as a qualitative research methodology, the study aims to evaluate the legal and regulatory frameworks for electoral participation, analyze the level of participation of PWDs, and identify the barriers they face. The findings of this research will be important for the NEBE and EHRC in assessing the adequacy and acceptability of measures taken to promote electoral participation and ensure compliance with international conventions. Overall, this chapter has laid out the groundwork for the study and provided readers with an understanding of what can be expected from the research.

2. Chapter Two: Literature Review

This literature review chapter provides an in-depth analysis of existing research on the electoral participation of persons with disabilities. Firstly, it examines the conceptual frameworks around disability and persons with disabilities, providing readers with a clear understanding of the terminology and definitions used in the research. Secondly, it explores the importance of electoral participation as a manifestation of human rights for persons with disabilities, highlighting the challenges and barriers they face in exercising their right to vote. Thirdly, it identifies the various barriers to electoral participation for persons with disabilities, including physical, attitudinal, and legal barriers. Lastly, it examines international best practices for ensuring electoral participation of persons with disabilities, outlining some of the strategies and measures that have been successful in promoting inclusive and accessible electoral processes. Overall, this literature review chapter provides a comprehensive analysis of the existing research on electoral participation of persons with disabilities, highlighting the key themes and identifying gaps in the literature that the thesis aims to address.

2.1 Disability and persons with disabilities conceptual frameworks

According to UN Declaration on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities stipulated that, “disabled person means any person unable to ensure by himself/herself, wholly or partly, the necessities of a normal, individual and/or social life as a result of deficiency rather congenital or not, in his/her physical or mental capabilities.” (United Nation, 2008)

The classifications of disability types it can be classified in 8 categories. This includes mobility/physical, vision, hearing, cognitive/learning, Psychological, spinal cord, head injuries & Invisible. (Disabled World , 2022)

Since the last two and a half decades, the global community has witnessed multi-directional changes in the overall understanding of disability and attitudes toward how people with disabilities should be treated and welcomed in the general political, economic, social, and cultural affairs of the polity to which they belong. The shift begins with the terminology we use to identify and refer to people with disabilities. In any dealings with these people, we must exercise caution in selecting appropriate wording to describe them. This is due to the fact that each term we use may reflect the attitude that one has toward these people.

2.2 Electoral Participation as a manifestation of human right of PWDs

Prior to the emerging human rights perception of disability in every sector, including electoral participation, which has been the emerging attitude towards disability and PWDs over the last two decades, the international community approached the various concerns of these people from various perspectives. These include medical approaches, charity model approaches, the social approach, which is currently acceptable, and the human rights approach.

Electoral participation is the method by which democratic countries decide the fate of all citizens, as citizens with disabilities have the same four basic needs as any other human being on the planet. Dignity is a quality of being worthy of esteem or respect, The importance of "autonomy" as a resource for the development of human self-reliance, Equality as a Tool for Appreciating Differences and Solidarity as a Concept as a Means for a Sense of Belonging, the main goal of the human rights perspective on disability is to maximize the visibility of these people in all political, economic, social, cultural, legal, and attitudinal land marks of society. (Shiuny, 2016) so that the electoral participating is clearly the manifestation of human rights for PWDs.

2.3 Barriers to Electoral Participation for Persons with Disabilities

The political participation of disabled people faces numerous challenges, and one of the primary barriers is the lack of accessibility. The majority of polling stations and political events are not designed to accommodate people with disabilities, making it difficult for them to vote or attend political gatherings. Discrimination is another significant challenge that hinders the political participation of disabled people, as they may be excluded from political decision-making processes and marginalized as potential candidates for political office. In addition, limited opportunities to engage in political activism can make it challenging for disabled people to advocate effectively for their rights. These barriers limit the ability of disabled people to fully participate in the democratic processes and shape the policies that affect their lives. (Priestley, et al., 2016)

Persons with disabilities face significant barriers to their full participation in political life, including communication, physical, legal/institutional, and attitudinal barriers. These barriers are compounded for those with multiple marginalized identities, such as women with disabilities or persons with disabilities who are refugees. While historical models of disability framed persons with disabilities as objects of pity or as needing to be "fixed," the social model of disability recognizes the need for society to make adaptations and remove barriers in order

to ensure that persons with disabilities can realize their human rights. The UN CRPD serves as a global consensus on the human rights of persons with disabilities, and efforts must be made to ensure that persons with disabilities are included in all aspects of political life, including as election observers. Such efforts must target the barriers that prevent full access and recognize the agency and capabilities of persons with disabilities. (Atkinson, et al., 2017)

Physical and psychological barriers to voting significantly reduce the turnout of disabled voters. These barriers include inaccessible polling locations, long lines, difficulty registering to vote, and the need for assistance when voting. The coronavirus pandemic has further exacerbated these barriers. Although laws and policies have been put in place to address these barriers, they are often not enforced or implemented, leading to a lack of accessibility for disabled voters. The psychological message sent by inaccessible voting systems also discourages disabled people from voting, reinforcing the notion that their voices are not valued. It is crucial for policymakers and local governments to prioritize the accessibility of voting systems to ensure that disabled voters can exercise their right to vote independently and without barriers. (DuHaime & Cohen, 2022)

various factors contribute to the lower political participation of people with disabilities, including lower resources such as education and income, social isolation, stigma and discrimination. Twelve studies conducted over the 1992-2010 elections consistently found lower voter turnout among people with disabilities, even with the option of voting by mail. Limited mobility, difficulty finding and getting to the polling place, and physical obstacles also contribute to lower voter turnout. While progress has been made to address physical obstacles in polling places, more needs to be done to ensure accessibility and accommodations for people with disabilities in the voting process. Further research and action are needed to address these issues and promote the political participation of people with disabilities. (Schur, et al., 2017)

The challenges faced by people with disabilities in the electoral process cannot be dismissed as minor issues. The legal disqualification of their ability to choose their assistants challenges the ideal of citizenship, which grounds the electoral legislation as authoritative and democratic in the first place. The clash between the ideals of universally applicable voting procedures and techniques and particular citizen-bodies circumscribed by state-endorsed regulations for disability highlights the practical fragility of the co-production and co-authorization of state and citizen-bodies in voting. Disability is not a fixed condition that can be easily compensated for by electoral managers or rules. It challenges the common perception of elections as

controlled and ordered, making the process appear more fragile and ambiguous. However, this does not suggest that the state of affairs is wrong in a way that can be mended once and for all. Instead, disability enables our thinking about the need for elasticity in the practical management of emerging challenges in the electoral process. (Gad & Dalsgaard, 2017)

The experiences of disabled people seeking to enter politics reveal the pervasive barriers and prejudices they face. Accessibility, resourcing, and ableism represent significant structural issues that affect a large section of society and require comprehensive measures and policies to address them. Although some interviewees reported positive experiences of the selection process, it was clear that a perception existed that parties had not always sought to make reasonable adjustments for disabled people. Moreover, assumptions regarding political campaigning and electioneering, along with a lack of resources to help disabled candidates meet these expectations, were felt to put them at a disadvantage. Therefore, greater flexibility in the ways selection processes, campaigns, and politics are run, and the establishment of a permanent and reliable source of financial support for disabled people seeking to stand for both selection and election, are imperative. (Evans & Reher, 2022)

In conclusion, the political participation of disabled people worldwide faces significant challenges that need to be addressed. Lack of accessibility, discrimination, limited opportunities for political activism, and various barriers to voting are among the primary obstacles that hinder the full participation of people with disabilities in democratic processes. The social model of disability recognizes the need for society to remove barriers and make adaptations to ensure that persons with disabilities can realize their human rights. Efforts must be made to ensure that persons with disabilities are included in all aspects of political life, including as election observers. It is crucial for policymakers and local governments to prioritize the accessibility of voting systems to ensure that disabled voters can exercise their right to vote independently and without barriers. Further research and action are needed to address these issues and promote the political participation of people with disabilities. Additionally, greater flexibility and support are necessary to ensure that disabled people have the same opportunities as non-disabled people to seek political office and engage in political campaigning.

2.4 International Best Practices for Ensuring Electoral Participation of Persons with Disabilities

The best practices identified for enhancing the political participation of disabled people in Europe include ensuring accessibility of polling stations and political events, providing training and support for electoral officials and staff, offering alternative voting methods, adopting inclusive policies, promoting political activism, creating partnerships and networks, and supporting research and data collection. These practices aim to increase the accessibility and flexibility of the democratic process, remove barriers, and promote the active involvement and representation of disabled people in political decision-making. (Priestley, et al., 2016)

Integrating a disability rights perspective into election observation is critical for ensuring that persons with disabilities can fully participate in the electoral process. This review highlights three key good practices for achieving this goal: including targeted questions on access of persons with disabilities in observer checklists, recruiting persons with disabilities to serve as observers and collect data, and conducting stand-alone election access observations to complement IEOMs. By following these practices, election observation missions can gather valuable data on the participation of persons with disabilities and provide nuanced feedback to policymakers and election stakeholders, ultimately leading to increased access to the political process for all. (Atkinson, et al., 2017)

There are several measures that can be taken to improve the accessibility of voting for people with disabilities. These include increased accessibility of polling places, voting equipment, and election websites; election monitoring in partnership with disability groups; mobile voting options; training for election officials and poll workers; outreach and education for people with disabilities; voting by mail; and reforms to election laws to conform to international standards. By implementing these measures, we can ensure that people with disabilities are able to exercise their right to vote and participate fully in the democratic process. (Schur, et al., 2017)

To overcome these challenges, it is necessary to take into account the different requirements and activities at each stage of the recruitment process, and ensure that they are accessible to all. This may require alternative formats of debating and canvassing, such as greater use of online activities, and the adoption of mentoring schemes. The establishment of financial support for disabled people, especially given the intersectionality of disability with other under-represented identities, should be provided by governments. The inclusion of more disabled

candidates and politicians in politics may reduce stigma and prejudice, and create a more representative and equitable democracy. Overall, it is imperative that political parties, institutions, and governments take active steps to ensure that disabled people have an equal opportunity to participate in the political process. (Evans & Reher, 2022)

the barriers faced by people with disabilities are deeply interconnected with broader social issues such as colonialism, racism, and capitalist exploitation. By recognizing these linkages, we can work towards a more inclusive society that values and respects the diversity of all its members. However, we must be cautious of piecemeal solutions that may inadvertently reinforce exclusionary attitudes and practices. In the case of e-voting, for example, we must be mindful of the potential risks and limitations of this technology, and ensure that it is deployed in a way that promotes accessibility and inclusion for all people with disabilities. Ultimately, the goal should be to create a society where everyone has an equal opportunity to participate and thrive, regardless of ability or any other characteristic. (Spagnuolo, et al., 2017)

While the idea that voting processes can affect turnout and inclusivity is not new, it has been conceptually underdeveloped and remains absent in many discussions of democracy and electoral integrity. The international community has developed assessment manuals and treaties to define standards for how elections should be run and to ensure inclusivity and political equality. However, these agreements are often disconnected from political theory, leaving the role of assessing and refining "best practices" to political actors. Modern political science has largely overlooked electoral practices as an area of study until the seminal work of Wolfinger and Rosenstone in 1980. Gradually, studies on inclusive voting practices have expanded to other established democracies beyond the US. Ultimately, inclusive voting practices can contribute to democratic outcomes by reducing inequality in the electoral process for citizens. (James & Garnett, 2020a)

2.5 Conclusion of the Chapter

In conclusion, enhancing political participation and access to voting for people with disabilities is critical for creating a more inclusive and representative democracy. Best practices include improving accessibility of polling stations, offering alternative voting methods, promoting political activism and partnerships, and integrating a disability rights perspective into election observation. It is also important to recognize the intersectionality of disability with other under-represented identities and to take active steps to ensure that recruitment processes are accessible. To create a truly inclusive society, we must address broader social issues such as

colonialism, racism, and capitalist exploitation that contribute to barriers faced by people with disabilities. Ultimately, inclusive voting practices can contribute to democratic outcomes by reducing inequality in the electoral process for all citizens.

3. Chapter Three: The International, Regional, and National Legal Frameworks Regarding the Electoral Rights of Persons with Disabilities

This chapter provides an overview of the legal frameworks that govern the electoral rights of persons with disabilities (PWDs) at the international, regional, and national levels. The chapter begins by examining the international human rights instruments that protect the rights of PWDs, with a specific focus on their right to participate in elections. It further explores the regional human rights systems in Africa and their provisions for the electoral rights of PWDs. Finally, the chapter examines the national legal frameworks in various countries and the extent to which they guarantee the electoral rights of PWDs. By analyzing these legal frameworks, this chapter aims to highlight the progress made towards ensuring the full and equal participation of PWDs in electoral processes, as well as the remaining gaps and challenges that need to be addressed.

3.1 International (UN) Human Rights Instruments and Electoral Participation of PWDs.

a) Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) as a Soft Law

Ethiopia ratified the UDHR on 3 July 1948, The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) is a landmark document that sets out the basic rights and freedoms that all human beings are entitled to. Among these rights is the right to equality and non-discrimination, which includes the right of persons with disabilities to participate fully in society. The UDHR recognizes that all individuals are entitled to the same rights and freedoms, regardless of their race, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth, or other status. (United Nations, 1948)

The right of persons with disabilities is an integral part of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The document recognizes the importance of ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their disabilities, can fully participate in society and enjoy their basic human rights and freedoms.

The UDHR contains several provisions that are crucial in inspiring persons with disabilities to exercise their political and electoral rights more fully. In particular, the document prohibits discrimination on any basis, which is essential in promoting equality and non-discrimination for all individuals. By recognizing and protecting the rights of persons with disabilities, the UDHR has played a significant role in advancing the cause of disability rights and promoting greater inclusion and equality in society.

b) The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) : A Binding Normative Foundational Instrument for the Political and Electoral Freedoms.

Ethiopia ratified the ICCPR in 11 June 1993, The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) serves as a vital safeguard for a broad range of civil and political rights, such as the right to life, freedom of expression and religion, security of person, and the right to participate in public life. Nonetheless, there are two key provisions in the Covenant that are considered crucial, Articles 2 and 26, which affirm the principle of non-discrimination. These provisions, though not exhaustive, are integral in ensuring that all individuals possess the same rights and freedoms, with no discrimination on any grounds, including disability. (United Nation General Assembly resolution 2200A (XXI), 1966)

The right to equality stands as one of the most essential human rights norms, and it is particularly critical in guaranteeing the effective implementation of all the rights protected under the ICCPR, particularly the political rights of persons with disabilities. By acknowledging the principle of non-discrimination and the right to equality, the ICCPR plays a vital role in advocating for greater inclusion, dignity, and respect for human rights across the globe, which benefits persons with disabilities as well.

c) Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) and Electoral Participation of Women with Disabilities

Ethiopia ratified CEDAW on 23 March 1981, CEDAW recognizes the right of women to participate in political and public life on an equal basis with men, including the right to vote and stand for election, and calls for the elimination of discrimination against women with disabilities and the promotion of their full and equal participation in all aspects of life, including in political and public life. While women with disabilities are not mentioned specifically, the term "women" encompasses both those with and without disabilities. The most relevant provision of CEDAW is Article 7, which requires states to take all measures to eliminate discrimination against women in their country's political and public life, including women with disabilities.

CEDAW calls for measures to be taken to ensure that women with disabilities have access to information and communication technologies, facilities, and services to enable them to participate effectively in political and public life, and to eliminate the barriers they face in exercising their political rights, including in electoral processes. (United Nations General Assembly, 1979)

d) International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (ICERD) and the Electoral Rights of PWDs

Ethiopia ratified ICERD on 10 June 1976, ICERD Convention's Articles 2 and 5 are crucial in upholding the right to political and electoral participation by prohibiting any form of discrimination. Ensuring the political and electoral participation of all groups, including persons with disabilities, is key to promoting peaceful coexistence among diverse groups. Although ICERD does not specifically mention persons with disabilities, its principles and provisions can be used to safeguard the rights of individuals with disabilities who face discrimination based on their race or ethnicity. The Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination has acknowledged the intersectionality of discrimination and called for the elimination of discrimination against all groups, including persons with disabilities. Therefore, ICERD's mandate to eradicate all forms of racial discrimination can be interpreted to include discrimination based on disability as well as race or ethnicity. (UN General Assembly resolution 2106 (XX), 1965)

e) Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD): The First Internationally Binding Instrument Exclusive to the Human Rights of PWDs.

Ethiopia ratified CRPD on 7 July 2010, The CRPD, or the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, recognizes the right of people with disabilities to participate in political and public life, including the right to vote and be elected. Article 29 of the CRPD specifically addresses the political participation of people with disabilities and calls on States Parties to ensure that.

States Parties shall guarantee to persons with disabilities political rights and the opportunity to enjoy them on an equal basis with others, and shall undertake to:

- a. *Ensure that persons with disabilities can effectively and fully participate in political and public life on an equal basis with others, directly or through freely chosen representatives, including the right and opportunity for persons with disabilities to vote and be elected, inter alia, by:*
 - i. *Ensuring that voting procedures, facilities and materials are appropriate, accessible and easy to understand and use;*
 - ii. *Protecting the right of persons with disabilities to vote by secret ballot in elections and public referendums without intimidation, and to stand for*

elections, to effectively hold office and perform all public functions at all levels of government, facilitating the use of assistive and new technologies where appropriate;

- iii. Guaranteeing the free expression of the will of persons with disabilities as electors and to this end, where necessary, at their request, allowing assistance in voting by a person of their own choice;*
- b. Promote actively an environment in which persons with disabilities can effectively and fully participate in the conduct of public affairs, without discrimination and on an equal basis with others, and encourage their participation in public affairs, including:*
 - i. Participation in non-governmental organizations and associations concerned with the public and political life of the country, and in the activities and administration of political parties;*
 - ii. Forming and joining organizations of persons with disabilities to represent persons with disabilities at international, national, regional and local levels*

In conclusion, the CRPD upholds the right of people with disabilities to participate fully and effectively in all aspects of political and public life, without any form of discrimination. This includes the right to vote, hold public office, and engage in other activities related to public and political life. Article 29 of the CRPD specifically addresses electoral participation, enabling people with disabilities to vote or contest elections with assistance, and providing access to assistive technologies. The Convention emphasizes the importance of ensuring accessibility in election proceedings and campaigns to enable people with disabilities to participate fully and effectively in the political process. (United nation Sixty-first session of the General Assembly by resolution A/RES/61/106, 2006)

3.2 The African Regional Human Rights System and Electoral Rights of PWDs

a. The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (The Banjul Charter)

Ethiopia ratified the Banjul Charter on 14 June 1998, The Charter's preamble espouses freedom, equality, justice, and dignity, all of which these people desperately need, and the Charter unequivocally calls for the abolition of all forms of discrimination based on non-exhaustive lists of grounds such as race, color, sex, language, religion, or political opinion. Though disability is not expressly mentioned, on the same grounds already addressed in

previous instruments, the Charter's non-discrimination provision could serve as an important tool in combating discrimination in political tournaments on the basis of disability. Articles 3, 5, and 19 of the Charter address the fundamental concepts of equality (at the individual level), the inviolability of human integrity and dignity, which apply equally to all human beings including person with disabilities, and the right to life. (Organisation of African Unity , 1981)

b. African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance (ACDEG)

Ethiopia ratified ACDEG on 21 November 2012, This Charter entered into force primarily with the goal of ensuring peaceful change of government and the realization of democratic power transfer in the states of the document is relevant to the electoral rights of PWDs living on the continent in a variety of ways. For starters, the Charter emphasizes human rights and democratic principles. It also promotes a representative government system with effective citizen participation in democratic, development, and governance issues, while recognizing universal suffrage as an inalienable right. In addition to these values, it assigns states parties the task of eliminating all forms of discrimination, particularly those based on political opinion, gender, ethnic, religious, and racial grounds, as well as any other form of intolerance. (African Union , 2007)

c. African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (The Women's Protocol)

Ethiopia ratified the Women's Protocol on 9 March 2004 , The primary goal of the instrument is to address the rights of women, including those with disabilities. Prior to this protocol, there was the Inter American Women's Convention aimed at protecting women's rights; however, the Convention was limited to the abolition of violence against women. This protocol, on the other hand, is a compilation of all women's rights, including their full participation in their country's politics.

The protocol's most important value is that it protects women with disabilities who face discrimination based on both their gender and their disability. (African Union , 2005)

d. Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression in Africa

Even if Ethiopia do not ratified the Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression in Africa, It is the result of the Resolution on the Right to Freedom of Expression, the primary goal of which was to broaden the scope of this right, which is guaranteed by Article 9 of the ACHPR. This declaration is relevant to the rights of people with disabilities, particularly in

terms of access to information and freedom of expression, without which the right to vote has no meaning. To that end, this Declaration may be invoked as a critical guideline for granting PWDs access to information and the freedom to express themselves using materials from their own communication media, such as Braille and sign language. In this regard, the document urges states to recognize diversity and provide marginalized groups like PWDs with pluralistic access to media and other forms of communication. (African Union , 2019)

3.3 The National Legal Frame Works and Electoral Rights of PWDs

a. FDRE Constitution and Electoral Rights of PWDs

The Ethiopian Constitution of 1995 has been the supreme law of the land for almost 28 years. It provides the foundational source of all rights to be exercised before, during, and after electoral procedures. Even though the Constitution does not explicitly mention disability as a prohibited basis for discrimination, Chapter 3, Article 13(2) reaffirms the need for Ethiopia to comply with International Human Rights instruments. (National Legislative Bodies / National Authorities, 1995)

As is the case with many international and regional human rights instruments, a positive interpretation of the Constitution's provisions is necessary to contextualize the rights in a disability-inclusive manner. This approach ensures that disability-related issues are adequately addressed and that people with disabilities can fully enjoy their political rights. While there is no explicit mention of disability, the Constitution can be interpreted to protect people with disabilities from discrimination, thus safeguarding their political rights.

b. Proclamation No.1133/2019 National Electoral Board of Ethiopia Establishment Proclamation

Since June 2019, this proclamation has been the country's working election law, through which the constitutional right of citizens to vote and be elected is expected to be implemented. As a result, Article 38 of the FDRE Constitution, as well as other supplementary rights enshrined in it, serves as the foundation for this legislation. Proclamation No.1133/2019 National Electoral Board of Ethiopia Establishment Proclamation does not explicitly mention persons with disabilities. However, the proclamation includes provisions that require the National Electoral Board of Ethiopia (NEBE) to undertake voter education and civic engagement programs that are accessible to all citizens, including those with disabilities. In addition, the proclamation mandates that NEBE takes into consideration the needs of marginalized and vulnerable groups

in its electoral processes, which could include persons with disabilities. Moreover, NEBE is required to establish a code of conduct that governs the behavior of election officials, political parties, candidates, and observers during the electoral process. This code of conduct is expected to prohibit discrimination based on various grounds, including disability, and ensure the equal treatment of all participants in the electoral process. In this way, the proclamation promotes the principles of non-discrimination and equality in the context of electoral processes in Ethiopia. (Federal Negarit Gaztta , 2019)

c. Proclamation No. 1162/2019 The Ethiopian Electoral, Political Parties Registration and Election's Code of Conduct Proclamations

Since October 2019, this proclamation has been one of the country's working election laws. The proclamation contains 164 provisions that govern electoral process, political party registration and code of conduct of the election. Let us see the articles that support the person with disability in electoral participation. Article 5 of the proclamation stated as election principles Any Ethiopian whose electoral rights have not been restricted by law or the decision of a court shall be eligible to vote or to be elected; however, he shall not be forced to vote or be elected and Each person shall only be allowed to vote by appearing in person. In article 15 of the proclamation establishment of polling station clarified that The Board shall establish polling stations at locations that take into consideration the special conditions of the disabled and other factors, and the address of the polling stations shall be announced to the public 15 days prior to the commencement of voter registration. Article 18 voter registration requirements limits the right by stating A person who is proved to be incapable of making decisions due to mental disorder as confirmed by the relevant authority or sufficient evidence cannot be registered. Article 22 also mention on particulars of the electoral roll the disability to be entered. Article 31 mentions that in criteria for candidature However, the endorsement signature for an independent candidate with physical disability shall not be less than 3,000. Article 32 candidates' nomination by political party stated that candidate with physical disability shall produce 1,5000 endorsement signatures for house of people representative seat and 750 for reginal counsel seat. Article 100 of the proclamation on government funding amount and eligibility criteria sub article 2 the amount of financial support that a political party receives, shall be determined by a directive to be issued by the Board based on the following criteria: including the number of people with disability candidates that it nominates, the number of people with disability members of the party and the number of people with disability in leadership positions. (Gazetta, 2019 - b)

d. Proclamation No. 1235/2021 A proclamation to Amend the Ethiopian Electoral, Political Parties Registration and election's code of conduct proclamation No. 1162/2019

This amendment was for the reason of Covid-19 that stated that for an independent candidate with physical disability shall secure the endorsement signatures of not less than 1,500 which only be applicable for the sixth national election. (Gazette, 2021)

e. Directive on Rules of Procedure and Code of Conduct for Security Personnel Assigned to Electoral Facilities and Activities No 12/2021

This directive is issued by the National Election Board on the basis of its mandate assigned to Election Law of the country which is addressed earlier. Article 9 sub article 13 stated Whenever an abrupt security crisis is encountered in the electoral facility or its surroundings performance of duties by security personnel shall give special attention to women, children, persons with disability and other persons in vulnerable situations. (NEBE, 2021 - a)

f. Directive on Accreditation, Working Procedures and Code of Conduct for International Election Observers No. 11/2021

This directive is issued by the National Election Board on the basis of its mandate assigned to Election Law of the country which is addressed earlier. Article 21 of International Observer Groups' duty to report sub article three clearly stated the value of including person with disabilities in the report by stating as obligation. (NEBE, 2021 - b)

g. Directive Issued to Mitigate the transmission of COVID-19 during Elections No. 9/2021

This directive of national election board of Ethiopia addressed the issue of covid-19 in the election of 2021 general election. Article 7 The Responsibility to Take COVID-19 Mitigation Measures Duties of the Board and Election Officers sub article 10 remarked The Board shall endeavour to ensure one-way flow for voters, and that polling stations and constituency offices are properly ventilated, with separate entrance and exit. When deciding the entrance and exit spots, the constituency office and polling stations shall consider accessibility to people with disability and other vulnerable people. (NEBE, 2021 - c)

h. Directive on Candidate Registration, Collection of Endorsement Signatures and Selection of Symbols no. 7/2021

This directive has lot of articles that mention person with disabilities. This includes Article 9 competing as an independent candidate Where the she is a person with disability secure endorsement signatures of at least 3000 for Federal and 1500 for regional eligible voters residing in the constituency where she is intending to contend Where he is a person with disability and if competing for a seat in a special zone, Nationality zone, Woreda or city administration council, he shall submit endorsement signatures of not less than 300 eligible voters Where the independent candidate is a person with disability and contending for a seat in kebele council, he shall submit endorsement signatures of not less than 50 eligible voters. Article 10 on the other hand If contending for a seat of the house of Peoples' representative the candidate shall submit at least 2000 endorsement signatures of eligible voters. However, if the candidate is a person with disability the required number endorsement would only be 1500. Regional council the candidate shall submit at least 1000 endorsement signatures of eligible voters. However, if the candidate is a person with disability the required number endorsement would only be at least 750. seat in a special zone, woreda, kebele or city administration council the candidate shall submit 300 signatures of eligible voters residing in the constituency. However, if the candidate is a person with disability the required number endorsement would only be at least 200. If contending for a seat of a special zone, woreda, kebele or city administration council the candidate shall submit 100 signatures of eligible voters of the kebele. However, if the candidate is a person with disability the required number would only be at least 50. Article 14 Collection of endorsement signatures states While collecting endorsement signatures the candidate or agent shall not discriminate people on the basis

of gender, economic status, disability or any other social identity. Article 39 on the other hand Responsibility of the board states the Board shall, while discharging its responsibility under sub-article (1) and disseminating such information duly takes into consideration the need to ensure accessibility to women as well as those having limited access to information and citizens that require special assistance such as persons with disability and the like. (NEBE, 2021 - d)

i. Directive on Conducting Voters' Registration; Directive No.6/2021

This directive states in article 18 persons that can be present in voter registration stations to include also Assistants of persons with physical disability who come to register. Article 25

particulars of the electoral roll also stated in the electoral roll to shall have columns for entering the disability or not disability condition and type of disability. (NEBE, 2021 - e)

3.4 Conclusion of the Chapter

The international, regional, and national frameworks that promote electoral participation of persons with disabilities offer several advantages. In conclusion, these frameworks recognize and uphold the inherent dignity and worth of all individuals, including those with disabilities, and affirm their right to participate in the political process without facing direct or indirect discrimination. By ensuring equal access to voting and electoral systems, these frameworks promote inclusive democracy and ensure that the voices of all individuals are heard, regardless of their limitations or challenges.

4. Chapter Four: Critical survey of electoral participation of PWDs the 2021 national election of Federal democratic Republic of Ethiopia data collection and analysis

This Chapter provides a critical survey of the electoral participation of persons with disabilities (PWDs) in the 2021 national election of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. The chapter utilizes a two-pronged approach to data collection and analysis: desk research and field research. The desk research section provides an analysis of the various stages of the electoral process, including registration, nomination, campaign, voting, and the announcement of results, and assesses the extent to which PWDs were included and accommodated in each stage. The section also examines the participation of PWDs as election observers. The field research section offers an in-depth description of the study participants and their responses to questions related to their experiences and perceptions of the electoral process as PWDs. By combining these two research approaches, this chapter aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the electoral participation of PWDs in the 2021 national election of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia.

4.1 Desk Research

The desk research as critical survey of electoral participation of PWDs in the 2021 national election of Federal democratic republic of Ethiopia considered the simplified electorally cycle typically consists of four stages. This includes Registration, Nomination, Campaign and voting. and last but not least the desk research includes the announced result and PWDs as observers.

4.1.1 Registration and PWDs in 2021 national Election of FDRE

At of 2021 June the estimated Ethiopians at voting age was 43 million. And out of this the rough estimation of the person with disability at voting age at that time was around 2.4 million considering that 17.6 % of the community is also for the voting age. At the end of the registration period estimated of 37 million voters registered. (Al-Jazeera, 2021) But the number of register person with disability voters has never been public as of the compiling of the desk research.

The registering polling station were about 43,017 stations and their accessibility condition was not found clearly in the desk research. But indirect reasons that affect the registration of voters including person with disabilities was delayed start of voter registration (due to material distribution and logistics), Low voter registration in the first few weeks of the schedule,

Imbalance between the number of polling stations and people who want to register to vote after the start of voter registration, especially in condominiums in Addis Ababa, Delays in payments for polling station workers & Special arrangements made in areas where voter registration was not possible due to security concerns are some of the challenges officially accepted by the NEBE. (NEBE, 2021 - f)

Positive development regarding registration of PWDs in 2021 national election of FDRE was the media advertisement regarding calling for voters’ registration which includes sign language in the Amharic language version. (NEBE, 2021 -g) Voter education outreach operations were not geared to voters with hearing impairments, particularly those residing in rural regions where traditional sign language is predominant. (IRI & NDI, 2021).

4.1.2 Nomination and PWDs in 2021 National Election of FDRE

Despite higher campaign funds granted to parties that nominate PWD candidates, political parties failed to include PWDs on their party lists. Only 99 of the 9,505 registered candidates are people with disabilities, accounting for 0.9 percent of the candidates registered by political parties for the Federal democratic republic of Ethiopia House of people representative elections and 1% for the regional council elections. (IRI & NDI, 2021)

When we look directly to the PWDs nominated for House of people representative out of the total candidates 1890 (one thousand eight hundred ninety) only 17 (seventeen) are nominated which out of them only 2 (two) are female. (NEBE, 2021 - h)

Figure 1 Educational Level of PWDs Nominated for House of People Representative in 2021 General Election of FDRE

The desk research found that the lowest educational level among the educational level of PWDs Nominated for house of People Representative in 2021 General Election was by the 2 (two) candidates 1 (one) male and 1 (one) Female and was below six grades. The highest educational level among the nominated was master degree and above which all of them are male candidate. And among them only one is an independent candidate where the others are nominated through the political party they belong.

4.1.3 Campaign and PWDs in 2021 National Election of FDRE

A campaign has two key elements. The first element involves promoting PWDs as candidates, demonstrating their qualifications and capabilities to prospective voters. The second element involves educating PWDs on the political process and the candidates themselves, allowing them to make informed decisions when casting their votes. By combining these two elements, the campaign can help to increase representation of PWDs

During the desk research for the first element, we didn't find any progress on it whereas on the second element from the political parties EZEMA showed initiative back in the campaign by including sign language in their campaign videos and banners. (EZEMA, 2021) But during the desk research we didn't find other parties' effort to word making their campaign accessible for all PWDs voters' categories.

4.1.4 Voting and PWDs in 2021 National Election of FDRE

The number of the turnout of voting of PWDs in 2021 national election of FDRE was not clearly identified though our desk research. However, according to an observer report, the unavailability of braille ballot frames on election day hampered independent voting for visually impaired voters. Stakeholders such as the Federation of Ethiopian Associations of Persons with Disabilities (FEAPD) and the Ombudsman's Office assessed polling locations on the day of voting for PWDs, and their assessments show that many are inaccessible to PWDs. (IRI & NDI, 2021)

4.1.5 Election Result and PWDs in 2021 National Election of FDRE

According to the publication of the election results for the 2021 National Election of FDRE for House of People Representatives, a total of 3 (three) PWDs candidates were elected to the House. 1 (one) of them was female. The educational background of the PWDs elected to the House of Representatives was university degree and above, with (2) two of them holding master's degrees and above. (NEBE, 2021 - i)

4.1.6 PWDs Observer in 2021 National Election of FDRE

Electoral participation of PWDs is not limited to being elected to the office or voting but also includes being active participant in observation of the election. Even if accessibility is still the issue for PWDs to vote, campaign and observe election there was positive development regarding observation according to Federation of Ethiopian Associations of Person with disabilities (FEAPD). (Federation of Ethiopian Associations of Persons with Disabilities, 2021)

4.2 Field Research

4.2.1 Description of Participants

Table 1 Potential Electoral Participant of 2021 General Election Interviewed

No	Age	Gender	Level of Education	Type of Disability	Acquired / Congenital
1	25	Male	High School	mobility/physical	Acquired
2	42	Female	University	mobility/physical	Born
3	37	Male	University	mobility/physical	Born
4	30	Female	Primary School	mobility/physical	Acquired
5	55	Male	Primary School	Vision	Acquired
6	24	Male	University	Vision	Acquired
7	33	Female	University	Vision	Born
8	46	Female	Primary School	Vision	Born
9	21	Female	High School	Hearing	Acquired
10	35	Male	High School	Hearing	Born
11	31	Male	High School	Hearing	Acquired
12	27	Female	University	Hearing	Acquired
13	25	Male	High School	cognitive/learning	Born

14	20	Male	Primary School	cognitive/learning	Born
15	24	Male	High School	cognitive/learning	Born
16	22	Male	Primary School	cognitive/learning	Born
17	46	Male	University	None	None
18	32	Female	University	None	None
19	37	Female	University	None	None

Nineteen (19) participants took parts in the thesis study. Out of the Nineteen (19) participants who took part in the study, sixteen (16) were person with disabilities and 3 of them person without disabilities from National Election Board of Ethiopia (NEBE) & Political Parties Joint Council.

Figure 2 The interviewed Disability Status

Figure 3 The Interviewed Disability Type

Figure 4 Sex of Interviewed

Out of 16 people with disabilities nine (9) were congenital. The participant had proportional diverse disabilities that includes: four (4) mobility/physical, four (4) vision, four (4) hearing and four (4) cognitive/learning. Out of the nineteen (19) eight (8) of the interviewed are female and 11 of them was man.

Figure 5 Educational Background of Participant

The participants have diverse educational background with five (5) primary school, seven (6) High School and Eight (8) University. In terms of age, the participant ranged between 21 and 55 years old.

4.2.2 Responses of Participants

The study findings were examined in order to achieve a full understanding of the data gathered. To portray the respondents' points of view, a verbatim presentation was adopted. Individuals with disabilities raised a variety of problems related to their disability kinds in response to the obstacles faced by individuals with disabilities in participating in the General election of 2021 in the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. Other responses from institutions asked provided their views/opinions as well.

- A. Mobility or Physical person with disabilities respondents stated that physical inaccessible polling centers and other facilities used in the electoral process as being one of the major challenges faced by them. And one of them mentioned that *“I has mobility in a wheelchair, but upon arriving at the voting location, I faced difficulties in exercising my right to vote. Despite being able to enter the voting compound without issue, I was unable to vote independently due to the fact that the designated ballot marking place did not accommodate my wheelchair. Additionally, the table for marking the ballot was not within reach while I seated in my wheelchair, further hindering ability to vote.”*

- B. One of the Blind respondents indicated that he has been voting in Ethiopian general elections for the previous five years in a row. During his participation in Ethiopian elections, including the 2021 general election, he never did it alone, which jeopardized his privacy.
- C. Many respondents in the deaf categories stated unequivocally that in the 2021 general election in Ethiopia, the party manifestos are unfamiliar to them because they are not communicated to their community. They also stated that it is difficult to elect the right party that reflects their interests, and the majority of them do not vote at all.

Respondents with disabilities reflected on the question *"From your experience, share with me some of the challenges that persons with disabilities face in participating in the electoral process in the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia - FDRE?"* After evaluating it, the results revealed that accessibility was the most significant concern, for all types of disabilities. the issue listed below also the part of the challenges that person with disabilities face to participate in the electoral process in FDRE.

- a) Inadequate information access includes Inadequate educational access and support services (brail, sign language interpreter, etc.)
- b) Disability-specific law for electoral participation is lacking.
- c) Inability to run for office due to a lack of money
- d) Lack of trust in the electoral process to accommodate PWDs

Figure 6 Electoral Participation of PWDs Respondents at 2021 General Election of FDRE

One of the PWDs Respondent with mobility/physical type of disability was observer in addition of voting in the electoral process of 2021 general election of Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia.

Respondents with disabilities who took part in the election process reflected on the question *"What improvement or otherwise did you observe during your participation in the 2021 General Election?"* After assessing it, the results indicated that voter registration was simple and closer to their home than voting day locations. Because the polling location is far away, 2 (two) of the registered PWD respondents did not vote at the voting day. Furthermore, the PWDs responder who was an observer reflected that 2021 is the first time he observed an election in addition to voting and feels that there was positive development in including people with disabilities in the electoral process of Ethiopia's 2021 general election.

Respondents with disabilities remarked on the question, *"What do you think are the barriers to electoral participation of persons with disabilities in the 2021 Ethiopian General Elections?"* The findings of the evaluation are that Inadequate information access includes insufficient educational access and support services (brail, sign language interpreter, etc.), a lack of disability-specific legislation for electoral participation, the inability to run for office due to a lack of funds, and a lack of trust in the electoral process to accommodate PWDs, was still barriers in the 2021 Ethiopian General Election of FDRE.

Last but not least respondents with disabilities remarked on the question, *"What electoral reforms can you recommend to improve electoral participation of persons with disabilities in Ethiopia?"* and their response analysis has revealed the following.

"Adopt person with disability specific legislation that promotes and protects the rights of all people with disabilities for electoral participation that includes make specified quotas or reserve seats for people with disabilities in local governments and the house of people representative."

- D. Representatives from National electoral Board of Ethiopia and Political Parties Joint Council were reflecting on the question we presented during the interview. Their compiled and analyzed answer are as following.

The representatives' remarked on the interview questions. The representative from national electoral board informed that there were multiple measures this includes selecting poll station one of the requirements was accessibility for PWDs, trying to incentivize political parties for nominating PWDs as candidate putting them in party leadership or even making them their party member, translating the electoral law into braille and distribution of 1400 of it was done, all video announcement in television from the board was with sign language, and PWDs candidate got capacity development training for the board.

The representatives from political parties' Joint council stated that there were some developments in the regulation that stated *“Political parties that fail to meet the minimum requirements of having a certain percentage of women and persons with disabilities in their candidate nomination, membership recruitment, and leadership positions will not be eligible for public funding. These requirements include at least 20% of women and 3% of persons with disabilities as candidates, at least 15% of women and 1% of persons with disabilities in membership, and at least 10% of women and 2% of persons with disabilities in leadership positions.”* Another respondent pointed out that while the idea of regulation promoting electoral participation for persons with disabilities is important, it was not fully implemented in the 2021 general elections. On the opposing party side remarked, recruiting persons with disabilities even for membership was challenging, given the political landscape in Ethiopia prior to the election.

The representatives unanimously reflected that Ethiopia has accepted all main documents and conventions concerning the inclusion of PWDs, obliging the state to actively protect their rights. PWDs have equal political, social, economic, and cultural rights under the Constitution. But on the ground despite some effort, it was not executed to its full extend in 2021 general election of Federal democratic republic of Ethiopia.

4.3 Conclusion of the Chapter

In conclusion, the critical survey conducted on the electoral participation of persons with disabilities (PWDs) in the 2021 National Election of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) reveals that PWDs face various challenges throughout the electoral cycle, including registration, nomination, campaign, voting, and observation. Despite the estimated 2.4 million PWDs at voting age, the number of registered PWD voters is not publicly known. Moreover, the nomination of PWD candidates by political parties was low, with only 99 PWD

candidates out of 9,505 registered candidates. The campaign efforts by political parties to make their campaign accessible to all categories of PWDs voters were limited. The unavailability of braille ballot frames and inaccessible polling locations on election day hampered independent voting for visually impaired voters. The election result showed that only three PWDs were elected to the House of People Representatives, reflecting a low representation of PWDs in the political decision-making process. Overall, the critical survey highlights the need for inclusive electoral processes that address the challenges faced by PWDs to ensure their full participation in the democratic process.

5. Chapter Five: Conclusions and Recommendations

This Chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations drawn from the preceding chapters, which analyzed various aspects of the electoral rights and participation of persons with disabilities (PWDs). The chapter begins with a summary of the main findings from the previous chapters, highlighting the progress made in ensuring the inclusion of PWDs in electoral processes, as well as the challenges that remain. The section then proceeds to present a set of recommendations and policy implications that aim to address the identified challenges and promote the full and equal participation of PWDs in electoral processes. These recommendations range from practical measures such as improving accessibility and accommodations for PWDs at polling stations, to broader policy changes such as strengthening legal frameworks and increasing political representation of PWDs. Overall, the chapter offers a comprehensive set of recommendations that can serve as a blueprint for policymakers, election officials, and civil society organizations seeking to promote the electoral rights and participation of PWDs.

5.1 Conclusions

This study aimed to analyze the Electoral Participation of Persons with Disabilities in 2021 General Election: Voices from Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. It tried to answer one major research question. *“Do the existing international legal instruments, to which the FDRE is a signatory as implemented in the 2021 general election, allow for effective guarantees of the electoral participation rights of people with disabilities?”*

With these aims, it started by clarifying the classification of disability types including mobility/physical, vision, hearing & cognitive/learning. It analyzed international, regional and national legal frameworks for electoral participation of PWDs.

The analysis found that FDRE has ratified the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR): Ethiopia ratified the UDHR on 3 July 1948, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR): Ethiopia ratified the ICCPR on 11 June 1993, Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW): Ethiopia ratified CEDAW on 23 March 1981, International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (ICERD): Ethiopia ratified ICERD on 10 June 1976 and Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD): Ethiopia ratified CRPD on 7 July 2010.

On the regional level FDRE ratified African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Banjul Charter): Ethiopia ratified the Banjul Charter on 14 June 1998, African Charter on Democracy,

Elections and Governance (ACDEG): Ethiopia ratified ACDEG on 21 November 2012 and Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Women's Protocol): Ethiopia ratified the Women's Protocol on 9 March 2004 but FDRE has not ratified the Declaration of Principles on Freedom of Expression in Africa. And then It analyzed the national legal frame works and electoral rights of PWDs starting form the FDRE constitution to directive of NEBE.

In conclusion, the analysis conducted with the support of desk research on the registration, nomination, campaign, voting, electoral result, and PWDs observer indicates that the International legal frameworks ratified by the FDRE were not effectively implemented in the 2021 General Election. Moreover, it was observed that also regional legal frameworks were also not practically exercised. This all can be exemplified by the following:

- Despite the fact that the international legal framework ratified by the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) clearly prohibits discrimination and promotes equality, the 2021 General Election was inaccessible due to inappropriate and difficult-to-understand campaign and voting materials. These barriers have been present in every cycle of the electoral process, preventing persons with disabilities (PWDs) from participating fully and equally in the electoral process, which constitutes clear discrimination.
- Despite the FDRE's adoption of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), which recognizes the full and equal participation of women with disabilities in all aspects of life, the 2021 General Election saw only 11.8% of the nominations for the House of Peoples' Representatives (HoPR) being PWDs women, while PWDs men accounted for 88.2% of the nominations.
- Despite the FDRE's ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), which recognizes the right of persons with disabilities to vote by secret ballot and the use of assistive and new technologies, the 2021 general election failed to provide even the bare minimum by neglecting to provide braille ballot frames for visually impaired voters to vote independently.
- Despite the FDRE's ratification of the International and regional legal frame works, which recognizes the right of persons with disabilities to participate in political parties of their choice, PWDs often refused to join opposing parties in 2021 general election due to the

toxic and undemocratic political landscape in the country, even when welcomed by such parties.

- Although the FDRE had ratified international and regional legal frameworks acknowledging the significance of establishing a fair and equitable electoral environment for all individuals, including those with disabilities (PWDs), the 2021 general election fell short in providing sufficient financial and empowering resources to PWDs who were vying for seats in the House of People's Representatives (HoPR). The outcome of the election served as a testament to this deficiency, with only 0.6% of the elected candidates being PWDs in the HoPR result for the 2021 General Election.

5.2 Recommendations & Policy Implications

In order to ensure electoral participation of persons with disabilities in Ethiopia, there are various policy and legal reforms that need to be implemented before the next general election. These recommended reforms include, but are not limited to:

- **Accessibility:** Ensuring that polling stations and voting materials are physically accessible and can be used by PWDs, including those with mobility, visual, or hearing impairments.
- **Training:** Providing training to election officials and staff on how to work with and support PWDs during the voting process, as well as how to use accessible voting technology and equipment.
- **Awareness-raising:** Raising awareness among the general public and PWDs themselves about the importance of voting and the rights of PWDs to participate in the electoral process.
- **Legal protection:** Enacting laws and policies that protect the rights of PWDs to participate in elections, including provisions for accessible voting materials, polling stations, and other necessary accommodations.
- **Inclusiveness:** Ensuring that PWDs are included in the planning and implementation of electoral processes, and that their needs and concerns are taken into account.
- **Collaboration:** Encouraging collaboration among government agencies, civil society organizations, and disability rights groups to ensure that the needs of PWDs are being addressed and that their voices are heard.

- Amendments to electoral laws to ensure accessibility in polling stations and voting procedures for persons with disabilities.
- Establishing legal provisions that prohibit discrimination against persons with disabilities in relation to electoral processes and guarantee their equal right to vote.
- Ensuring that laws and policies on disability rights are harmonized and consistent with international conventions and standards on disability rights.
- Adopting legal frameworks that promote the political participation of persons with disabilities, such as affirmative action measures and quotas.
- Providing legal protections and remedies for violations of the electoral rights of persons with disabilities. and providing accessible information and communication to persons with disabilities about their electoral rights and the electoral process.

In conclusion the study aimed to analyze the Electoral Participation of Persons with Disabilities in 2021 General Election in Ethiopia, focusing on the implementation of international legal instruments that ensure the electoral participation rights of people with disabilities. Despite Ethiopia ratifying various international and regional legal frameworks that protect the rights of PWDs, the analysis revealed that these frameworks were not effectively implemented in the 2021 General Election. The study found that PWDs encountered several barriers in the electoral process, including the inaccessibility of campaign and voting materials, lack of training for election officials, and insufficient financial and empowering resources for PWDs vying for seats in the House of People's Representatives (HoPR). The study recommended various policy and legal reforms to ensure the electoral participation of PWDs in Ethiopia, including accessibility, training, awareness-raising, legal protection, inclusiveness, and collaboration.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Participant Consent Form

PROJECT TITLE: Electoral Participation of Persons with Disabilities in 2021 General Election: Voices from Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia

Principal Investigator: Mekebib Tadesse Assefa, Online master in Electoral Policy and Administration Student, Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies – Pisa

What you should know about this research study:

- I am providing you with this informed consent letter so you may learn about the this research project.
- You have the option of refusing to participate or agreeing to participate now and later.
- You can alter your mind afterwards.
- Please carefully read this permission form. Before making a decision, ask any questions you have.
- Your participation is entirely voluntary.

BENEFITS AND/OR COMPENSATION

There will be no participant incentives for participating in this study.

CONFIDENTIALITY

This investigation's data will be used for the purposes of this research. In the publishing and distribution of the findings, you will not be identifiable by name or inference. None of these will be commercially exploited.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

This study is entirely voluntary. If you choose not to participate in this study, your future interactions with your institutions, their staff, and linked institutions will be unaffected. If you opt to participate, you have the right to withdraw your permission and stop participating at any time. Any failure to observe and fulfill agreed-upon appointments with the researchers will be deemed an implicit withdrawal, and the participant's consent in the inquiry would be terminated without his/her previous request. In the event that a participant in this inquiry is unable to complete the tasks agreed upon, participation will be discontinued without his/her agreement, and no remuneration will be granted.

AUTHORIZATION

You are deciding whether or not to take part in this study. Your signature confirms that you have read and comprehended the information provided above, that you have had all of your questions addressed, and that you have decided to join.

Name of Research Participant (please print)

Date

Signature of Participant

Appendix 2: Interview Guide for Persons with Disabilities

1. What is your age?
2. What is your educational level?
3. What is the type of your Persons with Disabilities?
4. From your experience, share with me some of the challenges that persons with disabilities face in taking part in the electoral process in Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia?
5. Did you participate in 2021 General Election?
6. If for Q-5 Yes. What was your electoral participation?
7. If for Q-5 Yes. What improvement or else do you observed during your participation in 2021 General Election.
8. What do you think are the barriers to electoral participation of persons with disabilities in 2021 Ethiopian General Elections?
9. What electoral reforms can you recommend to improve electoral participation of persons with disabilities in Ethiopia?

Appendix 3: Interview Guide for Entities

1. Were there any measures in place to support electoral participation of persons with disabilities in 2021 Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia General Elections?
2. Does the existing International legal frame works signed by the federal democratic republic of Ethiopia implemented in 2021 general election for effective guarantee for PWDs to enjoy and exercise their electoral participation?
3. What was some of the implementation that shows significant change for better in electoral participation of person with disabilities in 2021 general election of Federal democratic republic of Ethiopia?
4. What was the gaps of the implementation in 2021 general election of Federal democratic Republic of Ethiopia?